
**ENHANCING ELECTRIC VEHICLE EFFICIENCY WITH INDUCTION MOTORS
AND OPTIMIZED SOLAR POWER INTEGRATION**

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Abstract

The study explores the integration of induction motors in electric vehicle (EV) systems, emphasizing their suitability for urban driving due to high torque at low speeds. To enhance sustainability, photovoltaic (PV) panels are incorporated to directly power the induction motor using renewable solar energy. The research employs a modified sandpiper optimization (MSO) algorithm to determine the optimal sizing and placement of PV panels, maximizing efficiency. Additionally, an improved competitive swarm optimization (ICSO) algorithm is used to optimize power interfaces within the PV-powered EV system, addressing limitations of traditional maximum power point tracking (MPPT) techniques. A bidirectional DC-DC converter is implemented to facilitate bidirectional power flow and mitigate voltage imbalance. The methodology includes extensive simulations to validate and compare the proposed induction motor-driven EV system against state-of-the-art EV systems using brushless DC (BLDC) motors. The comparative analysis focuses on system efficiency, power output, torque characteristics, and overall performance. Principal findings indicate that the induction motor-driven EV system, when powered by optimally placed PV panels and fine-tuned through the ICSO algorithm, demonstrates superior efficiency and performance compared to BLDC motor-driven systems. The integration of these technologies offers a substantial improvement in sustainability and efficiency. The study concludes that utilizing induction motors in EV systems, enhanced with advanced PV optimization techniques, provides a viable and environmentally friendly transportation solution. This research contributes significantly to the development of sustainable EV technologies, promoting a greener future.

Keywords: Brushless Direct Current (BLDC) motor; Transportation; Electric Vehicle; Induction Motor; Optimal PV; Solar Energy**Abbreviations:**

MSO	Modified sandpiper optimization
ICSO	Improved competitive swarm optimization
EAIS	Enhanced artificial immune system
G2V	Grid to Vehicle
BLDC Motor	Brushless Direct Current motor
THD	Total Harmonic Distortion
VIN	varying input voltage

FFCS	Flywheel fast charging system
FC-EXP	Feedback controlled express station
ANFIS	Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System
V2G	Vehicle to grid
FET	Field Effect Transistor
PI	Proportional Integral
MILP	Mixed-integer linear program
AC	Alternating Current
MATLAB	Matrix Lab
PWM	Pulse Width Modulation
PHEV	Plug-in-Hybrid Electric Vehicle
HEV	Hybrid Electric Vehicle
HHO	Harris Hawks optimization
PEV	Plug-in-Electric Vehicle
MPPT	Maximum PowerPoint Tracking
EV	Electric vehicle
IM	Induction motor
PV	Photovoltaic

1. Introduction

EV system is a mode of transportation that utilizes electric propulsion instead of traditional internal combustion engines [1]. The vehicle's primary power source is electricity, which is stored in onboard batteries or capacitors. This stored electrical energy is then used to drive an electric motor that provides the necessary torque and power to propel the vehicle [2]. There are various sorts of electric vehicles, including battery electric vehicles (BEVs), module crossover electric vehicles (PHEVs), and mixture electric vehicles (HEVs) [3],[4]. Each type has its unique characteristics and power train configurations, but they all share the common feature of relying on electricity for propulsion. An electric motor is the primary power train component responsible for converting electrical energy into mechanical energy to drive the vehicle's wheels. The energy storage system stores the electrical energy, usually in the form of lithium-ion batteries, and provides the necessary power to the electric motor [5]. The power electronics system manages the flow of electrical energy between the battery and the electric motor, converting DC-AC and controlling motor speed and torque. EVs need to be charged regularly, and charging infrastructure includes charging stations, connectors, and cables to replenish the vehicle's energy storage [6]. The control system manages various aspects of the EV's operation, including motor control, battery management, and energy efficiency optimization. EVs offer several advantages over traditional internal combustion engine vehicles, including lower greenhouse gas emissions, reduced air pollution, quieter operation, and potentially lower operating costs due to fewer moving parts and lower energy costs [7]. As the world seeks more sustainable transportation solutions, EVs have become a promising alternative to conventional gasoline and diesel-powered vehicles.

The role of a Photovoltaic (PV) based power system [8],[9] in an EV is to provide a renewable and sustainable source of electricity to power the vehicle's electric motor. PV panels, also known as solar panels, convert sunlight directly into electricity through the photovoltaic effect. When integrated into an EV system, PV panels act as a supplementary power source or an alternative charging option, depending on the design and configuration [10]. One of the main functions of the PV-based power system in an EV is to act as an onboard charging system. PV panels can be installed on the EV's roof or other suitable surfaces, where they can harness sunlight and convert it into electricity [11]. This electricity is then stored in the vehicle's battery, providing an additional source of energy for driving the EV. By utilizing solar energy for charging, the EV reduces its reliance on grid electricity, promoting energy independence and sustainability [12]. By providing a viable charging solution in such locations, PV panels enable EVs to operate in regions with limited access to conventional charging infrastructure. This expands the potential reach and usability of EVs, making them a more practical and environmentally friendly option for transportation in various settings [13]. However, it's essential to consider the location and orientation of PV panels, as well as the available sunlight and the size of the PV array relative to the energy needs of the EV. Proper design, optimization, and control strategies are crucial to ensure the efficient and effective utilization of solar energy for driving vehicles. With careful integration and implementation, PV-based power systems offer numerous advantages and play a significant role in promoting sustainable and eco-friendly EV technology [14],[15].

Induction motors are well-suited for EVs due to their ability to deliver high torque at low speeds, making them efficient for city driving and stop-and-go traffic [16]. Induction machines, like asynchronous AC motors, are popular in Electric Vehicles (EVs) due to several technical advantages:

- 1. Simplicity:** Induction motors have a simpler design compared to brushed DC motors or synchronous AC motors, reducing manufacturing complexity and cost.
- 2. Robustness:** They have no brushes or permanent magnets, leading to lower maintenance requirements and longer lifespan.
- 3. High-torque:** Induction motors can provide high torque at low speeds, crucial for EVs to accelerate efficiently from a standstill.
- 4. Regenerative Braking:** Their inherent design allows for regenerative braking, converting kinetic energy back into electrical energy during deceleration, enhancing efficiency.
- 5. Variable Speed Operation:** Induction motors can operate efficiently over a wide range of speeds, enabling smooth acceleration and deceleration in EVs.
- 6. Scalability:** They are scalable to different power ratings, making them suitable for various types of EVs from small city cars to larger commercial vehicles.
- 7. Efficiency:** Modern designs and control techniques improve the efficiency of induction motors, contributing to extended driving range in EVs.
- 8. Integration with Power Electronics:** They integrate well with advanced power electronics, such as inverters and controllers, optimizing performance and energy usage in EVs.

These technical attributes make induction machines a compelling choice for propulsion systems in Electric Vehicles, balancing performance, cost-effectiveness, and reliability. The PV-based induction motor-driven EV system offers several advantages first, it reduces the reliance on traditional grid electricity, promoting energy independence and sustainability. Moreover, the combination of PV panels with the induction motor optimizes the energy efficiency of the EV [17]. This leads to an extended driving range and cost-effective transportation options for users. Furthermore, PV-based EV systems can be beneficial in areas with abundant sunlight or remote locations with limited access to conventional charging infrastructure [18]. The system provides a self-sustaining charging solution, enabling EVs to operate in regions without relying solely on external power sources [19]. However, challenges such as the intermittency of sunlight and the size and weight of PV panels need to be addressed in the design and implementation of the system. Efficient energy management and storage solutions [20] are crucial to ensure continuous operation, even in unfavorable weather conditions.

Our contributions. In this study, we investigate the performance of PV-based induction motor-driven EV systems under different operating conditions. The key contributions of the proposed methodology are summarized as follows.

1. By using the MSO algorithm, PV panel position and size are efficiently optimized, maximizing their energy capture from solar radiation. It directly impacts the overall efficiency and energy generation capacity of the PV-based induction motor-driven EV system.
2. Traditional maximum power point tracking (MPPT) techniques may face challenges in adapting to dynamic environmental conditions, potentially leading to suboptimal power conversion and utilization. By introducing the ICSO algorithm, the power interfaces are better optimized, addressing issues and improving the system's efficiency in converting PV-generated electricity to power the induction motor. It ensures that the EV system operates optimally under varying solar conditions, making it more reliable and efficient.
3. In an EV system, bidirectional power flow allows for energy to flow both from the PV panels to the induction motor and vice versa, enabling regenerative braking and energy recovery during deceleration. The control strategy of the bidirectional DC-DC converter ensures that power is efficiently transferred between the PV panels and the induction motor, improving the overall energy utilization and reducing energy losses. It enhances the system's energy efficiency and contributes to the EV's extended driving range.

Together, these algorithms significantly contribute to a more sustainable and efficient electric vehicle system, advancing the adoption of green transportation solutions. The following is the layout of the remainder of this document: Section 2 depicts the writing survey connected with the acceptance engine-driven EV framework. The essential investigations of the PV-based nonconcurrent engine-driven EV framework are made sense of in Section 3. The nitty gritty working course of the proposed EV framework model is examined in Section 4. The results and comparative analysis of proposed and existing models have been analyzed in Section 5. Finally, the paper concludes in Section 6.

2. Related works

In this section, we provide a comprehensive understanding of the state-of-the-art research related to PV-based induction motor-driven EV systems. Table 1 presents a summary of the research gaps identified from previous works.

Gabbar et al. [21] proposed a high-level computational knowledge method that utilizes the Upgraded Fake Safe Framework to improve FFCS execution on the side of vehicle zap. FFCS consistently coordinates with utility organizations to guarantee load adjusting and forestall framework disappointments, limiting energy costs and amplifying the utilization of clean energy assets. EAIS, as a high-level enhancement method, is utilized to tune the unique boundaries of FFCS for better reactions. Lymperopoulos et al. [22] introduced a progressive control component that utilizes the capacity foundation of the quick charging arrangement of the power transport to offer extra support (Concerning) the power matrix. The authors looked at the economic potential, technical viability, and aging effects of the storage network's batteries. Despite the Swiss TSO's regulatory requirements and the fast-charging system's primary purpose of fast-charging buses, the control mechanism demonstrated substantial flexibility in its current configuration. The authors also found that providing AS to the storage network could significantly decrease the energy-related operating costs of the buses.

Hou et al. [23], a decentralized charging scheduling system is proposed for standalone charging stations using the Blended Whole Number Direct Programming (MILP) plan. This tends to be the test of restricted transfer reality window choices accessible to clients. A numerical model brings choice factors and requirements into an equal machine programming model, giving a consistent arrangement. A continued offering framework because of game hypothesis and system configuration is utilized to take care of the cost arranging issue. The outcomes exhibit the viability of the framework concerning game hypothesis properties like individual sanity and specialist responsiveness, as well as the adequacy of mathematical trials with a typical productivity of 85% in uncovering halfway data. Tao et al. [24] proposed a Design for a full-bridge DC/DC converter with a synchronous rectifier and two clamping diodes. Terminal diodes were executed to stifle voltage swings on the optional side of the transformer and give changing capacity to the slacking leg, while coordinated amendment diminished exchanging gadget misfortunes. They investigated the standard of activity of the converter and the control strategy and determined the misfortunes of the exchanging gadget. The outcomes showed that the voltage vacillations on the optional side of the transformer were split and the converter accomplished 95% proficiency at 20-100 percent ostensible burden, which meets the necessities of the incorporated charger application.

Li et al. [25] proposed an effective strategy for sharing energy between the grid and a large charging station with photovoltaic panels and an energy storage system that benefits both EV users and the aggregator. They planned power allotment issues to direct the activity of the framework thinking about the discontinuity of photovoltaic boards. An upgraded agreement limit calculation was produced for genuine activities and relies upon the general fulfillment of EV clients and the aggregator. The recreation results show that this calculation produces numerous reliable and fitting agreement limit sizes contrasted with the current agreement limit power calculation. In Mehrjerdi's study [26], the attention is on long-haul dynamic scope quantification in microgrids. The microgrid

is furnished with different limits like a breeze, sun-oriented, miniature gas turbine, and energy stockpiling framework. The charging station looks like a flexible charging or generating device because the EVs there act like grid vehicles and can either supply power to the microgrid or adjust their charging times and speeds. A momentary arrangement is in progress to streamline the hourly activity of the microturbine, the energy stockpiling framework, and the electric vehicle charging station. The short-term operation of dispatch resources effectively contributes to the long-term plan for cost reduction and reduces planning costs by 28%.

Table 1-Summary of Research Gaps

Ref.	Methodology	Techniques used	Findings	Research gaps
[21]	Flywheel fast charging system (FFCS)	Enhanced immune system (EAIS)	artificial system Torque, angular speed, and energy storage	The DC-DC converter aspect is not the main focus.
[22]	Fast-charging stations for electrical buses	ABB and TOSA	State of battery health	The source's current THD level does not meet the necessary standards.
[23]	E-vehicle charging station scheduling	Mixed-integer linear program (MILP)	Efficiency, information revelation	This may result in power quality issues or instability.
[24]	Onboard charging for E-vehicle	Phase-shifted full-bridge DC/DC converter	Transformer ratio, switching frequency	Charging rates may vary due to fluctuations in battery temperature.
[25]	Storage system for E-vehicle charging	Time-of-use adjustment method	Contract capacity, charging cost	The devices are cumbersome to carry due to their size and weight.
[26]	Dynamic and multi-stage capacity expansion	Deep learning with an optimization algorithm	Planning cost, Expansion cost	They are not well-suited for use in PMDs.
[27]	DC-DC stage of E-vehicle charging stations	Two battery charging systems	AC-side terminal current	There is no emphasis on minimizing prediction errors.
[28]	Enhanced bidirectional E-vehicle charging station	Multi-step current control strategy	THD, source, and load currents	There is a significant amount of switching loss and noise interference.
[29]	Resource management model for charging station	Feedback controlled express station (FC-EXP)	Relative delay	Soft switching cannot be achieved under light loads.
[30]	Converter for grid to vehicle and vehicle to grid	Cascaded interleaved DC-DC converter	Flexibility, converter behavior	The use of pulse voltage can cause pulse current in the battery impedance.

Bayati et al. [27] have introduced two battery charging frameworks for electric vehicle charging stations because of a non-dissipative beat flow DC stage and a beat voltage DC stage. The above plan utilizes a flow distribution unit to produce a negative heartbeat flow and a very much planned control framework to charge and release electric vehicles at different voltage levels. The most recent plan is expected for high-power applications and limits unexpected changes in battery power brought about by the beat voltage technique. The precise control systems used in both models ensure that electric vehicles can be charged and discharged effectively. Useful outcomes show that these plans function admirably with lower yield power changes and wave contrasted with different

strategies. Balasundar et al. [28] have proposed a Bidirectional economical charging station for electric vehicles, comprising a bidirectional three-stage AC-DC converter, a bidirectional chopper, a static dissemination compensator, and a lithium-particle battery. This framework permits energy to move from the matrix to the vehicle as well as the other way around through bidirectional converters. The three-stage bi-directional inverter is constrained by the decoupled current and DC voltage control strategy. A multi-stage current control system is utilized to control the bidirectional switch. The framework is assessed utilizing PI and ANFIS regulators because of the DC voltage of the static dissemination compensator and the ongoing music of the organization. The ANFIS regulator better directs the DC circuit voltage and lessens the ongoing THD of the source. A multi-stage DC control strategy safeguards electric vehicle batteries from cheating and profound releasing.

Fescioglu-Unver et al. [29] have developed a model called FC-EXP, which utilizes criticism control to control the assets of an EV charging station. The objective of FC-EXP is to give need administrations to high-need vehicles while keeping an objective connection between the postponed seasons of ordinary and high-need vehicles. FC-EXP adjusts the allocation of resources in real-time to meet the different delay targets that the charging station sets based on its pricing policy. The model has self-checking abilities and has been displayed to answer unforeseen ecological changes quicker than conventional speedy help models. Mathematical examination shows that FC-EXP is compelling in accomplishing its objectives both progressively and in inconsistent state conditions.

Leal et al. [30] presented a flowed bi-directional interleaved DC converter for use in electric vehicle charging stations that can uphold both grid-to-vehicle (G2V) and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) advancements. The coupling method is utilized to diminish the ongoing wave experienced by the EV battery, which can consume or create capacity to or from the microgrid. PI regulators are utilized to control EV battery charging and releasing utilizing the little sign procedure. The trial results affirmed that the equipment arrangement used to test the control structure and the activity of the inverter is protected, efficient, and solid. This arrangement considered high current testing without compromising the high current voltages of a genuine EV battery.

3. Background study

The emergence of PV-based induction motor-EV systems is driven by the growing demand for sustainable and eco-friendly transportation solutions. These systems integrate solar PV panels with EVs, offering numerous benefits for both the environment and vehicle owners. One of the primary reasons for adopting PV-based induction motor-EV systems is environmental sustainability. By utilizing solar energy to power EVs, these systems significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions and decrease the reliance on fossil fuels, contributing to a cleaner and more sustainable environment. By harnessing solar energy, these vehicles can generate electricity on their own, reducing dependence on traditional electricity grids. This is particularly advantageous for EV owners in remote areas with limited access to charging infrastructure. The integration of PV panels also extends the driving range of electric vehicles. Solar energy can directly power the EV or supplement the battery, providing additional mileage during sunny periods. This feature can be

especially beneficial in regions with abundant sunlight, where vehicles can charge while driving. Another advantage of this system is reduced charging costs. By utilizing solar energy for charging, EV owners can take advantage of free, clean energy from the sun, lowering the overall cost of owning and operating an electric vehicle. Moreover, these systems help manage power peaks by utilizing solar energy during sunny periods. This reduces strain on the electricity grid during peak demand hours, contributing to a more stable and balanced power distribution. In terms of resilience, it can continue to operate during power outages, provided there is enough solar energy stored in the battery. This feature enhances the vehicle's reliability, making it a viable option during emergencies. From a business perspective, adopting to enhance the corporate image and marketing efforts of companies. By showcasing a commitment to eco-friendly practices, businesses can promote their sustainability initiatives and attract environmentally conscious customers. Additionally, many governments and municipalities offer incentives and subsidies to promote renewable energy and EV adoption. By incorporating PV panels into EV systems, vehicle owners can benefit from these incentives, making EV ownership even more attractive. Bharathi et al. [31] proposed a model for a solar-powered EV system that incorporates a BLDC motor. To optimize the performance of the PV-powered EV system, they used the Harris Hawks optimization (HHO) algorithm, specifically for the MPPT process. HHO algorithm proved to be more efficient than traditional MPPT methods, requiring less iteration to achieve optimal conditions, thus enhancing overall system efficiency. The speed control of the BLDC motor was accomplished using the PID controller in conjunction with the HHO-based MPPT technique.

Designing a PV-based induction motor-driven EV system comes with several challenges and problems that need to be addressed for the successful implementation and efficient operation of the system. Computing the appropriate size and optimal placement of PV panels on the electric vehicle is crucial for maximizing energy generation [21]. The system needs to be designed to capture sufficient solar energy to power the induction motor effectively while ensuring that the PV panels do not obstruct the vehicle's aerodynamics and functionality [22], [23]. To design an efficient MPPT algorithm is essential to extract the maximum available power from the PV panels. Different MPPT techniques [21], [32], have their advantages and limitations, and selecting the most suitable one for the specific induction motor-EV system is critical to ensure the highest energy conversion efficiency. The power electronics play a vital role while the induction motor typically requires AC for operation [24]. Thus, appropriate power electronics, such as DC-DC converters and inverters, are needed to convert and control the power flow between the PV panels and the motor [25], [26]. Selecting suitable and high-performance energy storage solutions is crucial for the overall performance and range of the EV, as it impacts the ability to utilize solar energy effectively. Furthermore, integrating the PV panels, induction motor, power electronics, and energy storage components into a cohesive and efficient system is a challenging task [27], [28]. Finally, the system may initially involve higher costs due to the integration of solar panels and advanced power electronics. Balancing the cost of implementation with the benefits and long-term savings is essential for making the system economically viable and appealing to consumers. Addressing these challenges requires AI-based techniques, involving expertise in electrical

engineering, control systems, power electronics, and renewable energy technologies [29], [30]. Advances in technology are continuously improving the design and efficiency of PV-based induction motor-EV systems, making them a promising and eco-friendly solution for sustainable transportation.

- To design PV based induction motor-driven EV system, considering the integration of PV panels, battery storage, and an induction motor for propulsion.
- To evaluate the performance characteristics of BLDC and induction motor-based EV systems, including efficiency, torque-speed characteristics, and overall system reliability.
- To assess the energy efficiency and range capabilities of the induction motor-operated EV under different driving conditions, such as varying speeds, terrains, and loads.
- To analyze the dynamic response of the induction motor-based EV system, including acceleration, braking, and regenerative braking capabilities.
- To validate the performance of the induction motor-operated EV system through different scenarios to provide predictions and insights into operational characteristics.

Specialized guidelines administering electrical and telecom items expect that the DC supply voltage of electric vehicle charging frameworks is under 60 V. Notwithstanding, charging frameworks equipped for creating voltages more prominent than 60 V should meet the voltage prerequisites for electric vehicle gear. Figure 1 depicts our PV-based induction motor EV system model. To match the output voltages of each converter, we use series-connected bi-directional DC-DC converters. The info voltage of each level converter utilizes a voltage that can drive the normal entryway speaker simulated intelligence, A_j , A_k , and the framework setup involves the block enhancer voltage as the stock voltage, utilizing a field-impact semiconductor switch on the adverse terminal of the information power supply A_m , A_n . To address the difficulties of PV board size and situation, we utilize a Changed Sand Line Streamlining (MSO) calculation that gives upgraded PV designs. Furthermore, we introduce the improved competitive swarm optimization (ICSO) algorithm to adjust the power interfaces in the PV-powered EV system, overcoming issues encountered in traditional MPPT techniques. Additionally, the implementation of bidirectional DC-DC converters effectively addresses voltage unbalance problems and enables precise control of bidirectional power flow.

Fig. 1 Overall conceptual structure of the proposed PV-based induction motor-driven EV system

4. Proposed Methodology

In this section, we present the proposed methodology for a PV-based induction motor-driven EV system, which consists set of processes such as PV panel sizing and placement, power interface adjustment, and bidirectional DC-DC converter.

4.1 PV panel sizing and placement

PV panel sizing and placement refer to the process of determining the appropriate size and optimal location in a solar power system. PV panels are the key components that convert sunlight into electrical energy, and their size and placement are crucial for maximizing the energy output and overall efficiency of the solar system. PV panel sizing involves determining the number of panels and their capacity required to meet the energy demands of specific applications, such as charging EVs. It is essential to accurately size the PV panels to ensure they can generate enough electricity to power the EV system under different operating conditions, including varying levels of sunlight and energy consumption. It focuses on finding the best physical location for installing PV panels. Factors such as the orientation of the panels relative to the sun, shading from nearby objects or structures, and available roof or ground space are taken into account during the placement process. The goal is to position the panels in a way that maximizes solar exposure throughout the day, optimizing the amount of energy they can capture from the sun. By accurately sizing the panels and strategically placing them to receive optimal sunlight, the solar system can generate more electricity, reduce dependency on grid power, and contribute to a greener and more sustainable energy solution.

The modified sandpiper optimization (MSO) algorithm is a nature-inspired technique used for PV panel sizing and placement in solar power systems. This algorithm takes inspiration from the foraging behavior of sandpipers, which are migratory birds known for their efficient search and exploration strategies. In the context of PV panel sizing, the MSO algorithm optimizes the number and capacity of PV panels required to achieve the desired energy output for a given solar system. The algorithm explores different combinations of panel sizes and numbers, iteratively adjusting

the parameters to find the most efficient configuration that maximizes energy production while considering factors like available space and budget constraints. For PV panel placement, the MSO algorithm optimizes the physical location and orientation of the panels to maximize solar exposure. It takes into account the sun's position throughout the day, the tilt angle of the panels, and potential shading effects from nearby objects. By intelligently exploring different panel positions, the algorithm identifies the optimal arrangement that captures the most sunlight and ensures consistent energy generation.

The target of the streamlining system is to distinguish an ideal arrangement that joins various goals into one. In enhancement, there are two arrangements of imperatives, specifically balance and disparity, and the objective is to limit or amplify the requirements.

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{Minimize} \\ \text{Maximize} \end{array} : f(z) = F_1(z) \quad (1)$$

An extra factor CA is utilized for the calculation of new hunt specialist positions to keep away from the impact evasion between their adjoining sandpipers.

$$\vec{C}_{sb} = C_p \times \vec{A}_{sb}(z) \quad (2)$$

where means the place of the pursuit specialist that doesn't meet with one more hunt specialist, characterizes the flow position of the pursuit specialist, z signifies the momentum emphasis, and CA characterizes the development of the inquiry specialist in the hunt space.

$$C_p = C_F - (z \times (C_F / \text{Max}_{iterations}))$$

where, (3)

$$z = 0, 1, 2, \dots, \text{Max}_{iterations}$$

where is the control recurrence for changing the variable, which diminishes directly from Cf to 0. For instance, if the boundary Cf is set to 2, the variable constantly diminishes from 2 to 0. After crash evasion, the hunt specialists merge in the best-neighbor course.

$$\vec{X}_{sb} = C_Q \times (\vec{A}_{bst}(z) - \vec{A}_{sb}(z)) \quad (4)$$

where demonstrates that the hunt specialist's position toward the best-fit search specialist (ie, the one with the least wellness esteem) is an irregular variable liable for better investigation. It is determined as follows:

$$c_Q = 0.5 \times R_{And} \quad (5)$$

where rand is an irregular number in the reach [0, 1]. At last, the pursuit specialist or sandbox can refresh its situation to match the best hunt specialist.

$$\vec{D}_{sb} = \vec{D}_{sb} + \vec{P}_{sb} \quad (6)$$

where characterizes the hole between the most reasonable pursuit specialists. During relocation, gerbils can continually change their speed and approach. They utilize their wings to build their level. Shredders make a spiraling way of behaving while going after prey. This conduct in the 3D plane is portrayed underneath.

$$m^i = \text{Radius} \times \sin(H) \quad (7)$$

$$n' = \text{Radius} \times \cos(H) \quad (8)$$

$$w' = \text{Radius} \times H \quad (9)$$

$$r = u \times e^{gV} \quad (10)$$

where Span is the sweep of each twisting turn, and H is a variable in the reach $[0 \leq k \leq 2\pi]$. The spiral's shape is determined by constants U and V, and the natural logarithm's base is E. The spiral's shape becomes more complex when these constants are greater than 1. In this way, the refreshed place of the pursuit specialist is determined as follows.

$$\vec{A}_{sb}(z) = (\vec{D}_{sb} \times (m' + n' + d')) \times \vec{A}_{bst}(z) \quad (11)$$

where it stores the best and optimal solution and updates the positions of other search agents. The work process for estimating and setting PV boards utilizing MSO is given in Table 2.

Table 2-Algorithm 1 PV panel sizing and placement using MSO

Input: PV data, design constraints, maximum iteration	
Output: PV panel sizing and placement	
1.	Initialize the random population
2.	The aim is to minimize or maximize constraints.
	<i>Minimize</i> : $f(z) = F_1(z)$
	<i>Maximize</i>
3.	If $i=0, j=1$
4.	While Do
5.	Compute collision avoidance function $\vec{C}_{sb} = C_p \times \vec{A}_{sb}(z)$
6.	C_Q is computed $c_Q = 0.5 \times R_{And}$
7.	If not discarded then
8.	Updated position of search agent $\vec{A}_{sb}(z) = (\vec{D}_{sb} \times (m' + n' + d')) \times \vec{A}_{bst}(z)$
9.	Update the final values
10.	The classes are evaluated for accuracy
11.	End

4.2 Power interface adjustment

Power interface adjustment refers to the process of optimizing the power transfer between different components in a power system. In the context of PV powered EV system, power interface adjustment involves optimizing the power flow between the PV panels, the energy storage system, and the electric motor that drives the vehicle. The main objective of power interface adjustment is to ensure that the power generated by the PV panels is efficiently used to meet the energy demands of the electric vehicle. This includes optimizing the charging and discharging of the batteries, controlling the power delivered to the motor for propulsion, and managing any excess energy that can be fed back to the grid or stored for later use. An improved competitive swarm optimization (ICSO) algorithm, as mentioned in the previous context, is used for power interface adjustment in PV-powered EV systems. The ICSO algorithm addresses the issues faced by traditional MPPT techniques, which are responsible for optimizing the power output of the PV panels. By using the ICSO algorithm, the power flow within the PV system is dynamically adjusted to maximize energy capture and utilization, leading to improved efficiency and overall performance of the EV. Let's

say this is the Gth iteration and contests were held. After the kth challenge, the triumphant molecule of the new age continues as (e) the horrible molecule, for example, the position vector, is refreshed as follows:

$$w_{K,g}(F+1) = w_{K,g}(F) + D_{K,g}(F+1), \quad (12)$$

where $V_{1,k}(G+1)$ is the cutting edge speed vector refreshed as:

$$D_{K,g}(F+1) = Ea_1(G,F)D_{K,g}(F) + Ea_2(G,F)[w_{\omega,g}(F) - w_{K,g}(F)] + \phi Ea_3[\bar{w}_g(F) - w_{K,g}(F)] \quad (13)$$

where the random vectors rn_1 , rn_2 , and rn_3 are the center of the collection of particles that are either adjacent to one another or sufficiently close to one another is referred to as the weighting factor $xk(G)$. This neighborhood field already exists. For continuous cases, velocity and position vectors are used. In a special case, the neighborhood includes the entire group, and $xk(G)$ is the global mean position of the particles in iteration G. In an exceptional case, for example, that of the $swi(k)$ arrangement factors in this review, other refreshing systems should be utilized.

$$\begin{cases} w_{K,g}(Ea, F+1) = w_{\omega, g}(Ea, F), \\ p_{l,g}(E\bar{a}, F+1) = w_{K,g}(E\bar{a}, F), \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where Ea signifies the haphazardly produced records of the parts of molecule p , and Rb the unselected files demonstrate that the triumphant molecule $xw_{k}(G)$ chooses and duplicates a portion of its parts to the up and coming age of losing particles, while the unselected parts continue as before as $xl_{k}(G)$. To achieve satisfactory outcomes, the corresponding modifications to the decision variables must be implemented. To implement the ICSO algorithm for the constrained problem, the penalty function is added to the original objective function.

$$r_{ca} = \sum_{G=0}^Q \sum_{U=0}^{A_u} \omega_{rda,u} R_{ca,u}(g), \quad (15)$$

$$r_{ca,u}(g) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if constraint } O \text{ is obeyed,} \\ B, & \text{if constraint } O \text{ is violated,} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where h is the constraint weighting factor, is a large positive number, and f fitness function.

$$t(w) = I_m + r_{ca} \quad (17)$$

After the opposition, the horrible molecule should gain from the triumphant molecule. So, the changes are utilized to work on the presentation of this specific issue. Let $t(w)$ be the normal wellness of the ongoing multitude. Fitness is assessed for both the winning and losing particles following the competition.

$$t(w_{\omega,g}(F)) \geq \bar{t}(F), F = Interior \quad (18)$$

$$t(w_{K,g}(F)) \leq \bar{t}(F), F = Interior \quad (19)$$

$$t(w_{\omega,g}(F)) \leq \bar{t}(F) \leq t(w_{K,g}(F)), \text{ original learning} \quad (20)$$

The competitive behavior of the swarm members, such as competition for resources or survival, may be adjusted or modified in the CSO algorithm to encourage more effective exploration and exploitation of the solution space. The specific modifications in the ICSO algorithm vary based on the problem domain and the objectives of the optimization task. By providing superior MPPT performance, optimizing power interfaces, and enhancing overall system efficiency, the ICSO algorithm contributes to the development of a more sustainable and environmentally friendly electric vehicle solution.

4.3 Bidirectional DC-DC converter

The bidirectional DC-DC converter is an essential component in the PV-based induction motor-driven EV system. It serves the crucial role of managing the power flow between the PV panels, the battery storage system, and the induction motor. The converter empowers bi-directional power move, and that implies it can effectively oversee power in the two bearings, from the PV boards to the battery during charging and from the battery to the engine during driving. To attain the necessary charging voltage, each inverter's output voltage is matched. The information voltage of each level converter utilizes a voltage fit for driving a typical entryway intensifier, and the framework setup involves the door enhancer voltage as the stockpile voltage utilizing an FET switch on the adverse terminal of the information power supply. Fig. 2 depicts the structure of a multistage bidirectional DC-DC converter. B1, B2, B3, and B4 are load-side expert switches that permit work with various information power for each level in the staggered converter addressed by v_g MLDC and the amount of the voltages as per the exchanging condition of the staggered converter. The switches are turned here and there founded on got power, which is moved from the source to the capacity framework power and charged as a unidirectional current course through the associated exchanging gadget. The multi-level bidirectional converter connects the buck-boost converter in series [31]. Hence, the buck converter's characteristics were first examined. The inductor current wave relies upon the predefined voltage, recurrence, and normal obligation proportion of the inverter. The wave of the ongoing coursing through the inductor (I) and the wave of the resulting voltage brings about the wave of the inductor current (A_R). On the off chance that the ongoing moving through the inductor is characterized as M_I , the inductor current wave is communicated as.

$$\gamma_{M_I} = \frac{A_R}{I} v_g D(1-D) \quad (21)$$

Similarly, the output voltage v_{out} is related to the input voltage v_{in} and duty ratio C . The voltage ripple of the output voltage is proportional to the output current and the equivalent series resistance of the inductor. The capacitor on the output side is responsible for smoothing out the ripple, and the capacitor value is determined by the load current and allowable ripple. Understanding the buck-boost converter's behavior and designing the multi-level bidirectional converter require these characteristics.

$$\gamma_{M_{V_{out}}} = \frac{v_g D(1-D) A_R^2}{8ID} \quad (22)$$

Contrasted and a customary lift converter, the inductor current and voltage wave of the proposed staggered still up in the air by the quantity of levels and the obligation proportion of the converter. The greatest wave state of the proposed converter is the point at which the quantity of levels is equivalent to the most extreme wave esteem in the customary buck-help converter. The info voltage of a staggered inverter is meant by v_g MLDC, which is comprised of N numbers. A deterministic number of levels, NMLDC, is expected to create the resulting voltage V_{out} from the info voltage v_g MLDC. The number of converters that perform beat width adjustment (PWM) between $0 < \text{obligation} < 1$ is characterized as NMLDC. If the exchanging condition of the inverter is running, it is excluded from the quantity of inverters performing PWM.

Fig. 2 Structure of multi-level bidirectional DC-DC converter

Through this definition, the obligation proportion of the result voltages, V_{out} and CMLDC, can be communicated.

$$v_{out} = v_{gMLDC} (B_{MLBD} + (D_{MLBD} - 1)B_{MLBD}) \quad (23)$$

$$D_{MLBD} = v_{out} - \left(\frac{v_{gMLDC} * (B_{MLBD} - 1)}{v_{gMLDC} * B_{MLBD}} \right) \quad (24)$$

The current ripple generated by each level in the multi-level converter can be canceled out by using the overlapping effect of the output voltages from each level. When the output voltage of one level decreases, the output voltage of the adjacent level increases and the two voltages overlap each other, resulting in the cancellation of the current ripple. This overlapping effect is achieved by controlling the duty ratio of each switch in the converter, which adjusts the output voltage of each level.

$$Cancel \gamma_{MI} = \frac{B_{MLBD} \left(D_{MLBD} - \frac{B_{MLBD} * D_{MLBD}}{B_{MLBD}} \right) \left(\frac{(B_{MLBD} * D_{MLBD}) + 1}{B_{MLBD}} - D_{MLBD} \right)}{D_{MLBD} (1 - D_{MLBD})} \quad (25)$$

Its bidirectional power flow capability, voltage regulation, energy storage, and dynamic power control contribute to the overall performance, efficiency, and sustainability of the electric vehicle system.

5. Results and Discussion

In this section, we present the results and comparative analysis of the proposed PV-based induction motor-driven EV system [33], [34] and existing PV-based BLDC motor-driven EV system [31]. Our proposed model consists of a set of processes such as PV panel sizing using the MSO algorithm, power interface optimization using the ICSO algorithm, and also utilized bidirectional DC-DC converter for better power flow. Likewise, in [31] they used the HHO algorithm for power interface optimization. MATLAB Simulink was used for the simulations, and various scenarios were tested to evaluate the converters' performance. The performance of proposed and existing models has been analyzed with different measures such as current ripple, voltage ripple, and system efficiency. Table 3 provides a comprehensive description of the simulation parameters utilized in the study for the PV-based induction motor drive system. These parameters are crucial for accurately modeling and analyzing the system's performance. The bidirectional DC-DC converter, a key component of the system, operates with an input voltage of 12V and includes an output inductor with an inductance value of 200 μ H and an output capacitor with a capacitance of 10 μ H. Because the converters are connected in series, their output voltages, V , can overlap.

Table 3 Simulation parameter description

Module	Parameter	Value
Converter	Converter input voltage	12 V
	Output inductor inductance	200 μ H
	Output capacitor capacitance	10 μ H
	Output load resistance	600 Ω
	Switching frequency	20 kHz
PV panel	Power at STC	250W
	Power at PTC	227.8W
	Voltage at Max Power	35.2V
	Current at Max Power	7.1A
	Open Circuit Voltage	43.22V
	Short Circuit Current	7.76A
Induction motor	Nominal Operating Cell Temp	43.5 $^{\circ}$ C
	Nominal power	149.2 kVA
	Line voltage	460 Vrms
	Frequency	60Hz
	Stator resistance	0.0015 Ω
	Stator inductance	0.0003 H
	Rotor resistance	0.0092 Ω
Rotor inductance	0.0003 H	

Mutual inductance	0.0105 H
Friction factor	0.08Nms
Pole pair	2
Power factor	0.88

Moving on to the PV panel parameters, we have essential performance metrics under various conditions. The power output of the PV panel is characterized by two measures: 250W under STC and 227.8W under PTC. Moreover, the panel exhibits a voltage of 35.2 volts and a current of 7.1A at its maximum power point. The PV panel's behavior is further described by its open circuit voltage of 43.22V and short circuit current of 7.76A. Additionally, the nominal operating cell temperature is specified at 43.5°C, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of the PV panel's performance. Concerning the induction motor, various electrical and mechanical parameters are outlined. The motor's nominal power is indicated as 149.2 kVA, and it operates with a line voltage of 460V at a frequency of 60Hz. The stator and rotor windings exhibit resistances of 0.0015Ω and 0.0092Ω, respectively, while the stator and rotor inductances are measured at 0.0003 H. The mutual inductance between the stator and rotor windings is recorded as 0.0105H. Additionally, the motor's performance is influenced by a friction factor of 0.08Nms, and it features 2 pole pairs. The power factor of the induction motor is specified as 0.88, further characterizing its behavior under different load conditions.

Fig. 3 Simulink model for PV-based induction motor drive EV system

The MATLAB/Simulink simulation model, as depicted in Fig. 3, is developed for the PV-based induction motor drive EV system. The system employs a 4 kW induction motor as the primary drive, necessitating the design of a corresponding Solar PV system capable of generating the required power. To achieve this, a Solar PV string comprising 16 PV panels, each with a power output of 250 W, is assembled to match the 4 kW motor power requirement. The bidirectional DC-DC converter is tailored to produce a DC output of 816V at 4 kW, with a switching frequency of 10 kHz. The converter's key components, inductance (L) and capacitance (C) are calculated as 8.1 mH and 10 μ F, respectively, to ensure efficient operation. Fig. 4 showcases the results of the proposed bidirectional DC converter. The arm voltages are presented in subfigures (a) and (b), with (b) offering an enlarged view to provide a clear representation of the voltage waveforms. Similarly, subfigures (c) and (d) depict the pole voltage, with (d) providing an amplified perspective of (c). Furthermore, considering the operation of the induction motor, it is crucial to assess its performance under different load conditions. Fig. 5 illustrates the speed of the induction motor drive under a no-load condition and the starting torque of the motor. At the starting

condition, the speed experiences a drop, and the torque is notably high. As the load condition increases, the speed gradually rises until it reaches the rated speed, and the torque decreases compared to the starting torque, as indicated in Fig. 6.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 4 Characteristic results of proposed bidirectional DC-DC converter with (a) arm voltage (b) enlarged arm voltage (c) pole voltage (d) enlarged pole voltage

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5 Results of the proposed model for PV-based induction motor-driven EV system with No-Load condition (a) speed (b) torque

Fig. 6 Results of the proposed model for PV-based induction motor-driven EV system with Load condition (a) speed (b) torque

5.1 Comparative analysis for current ripple

Table 4 presents a comparison of current ripple (γ_{AL}) values for the proposed PV-based induction motor drive EV system and the existing PV-based BLDC motor drive EV system. The values are analyzed with varying input voltage (V_{IN}) and duty cycles. Overall, our proposed PV-based induction motor drive EV system demonstrates lower current ripple values across different duty cycles and input voltages compared to the existing PV-based BLDC motor drive EV system. This signifies improved current stability and smoother operation in our proposed system. When analyzing specific data points, we observe that at a duty cycle of 0.1, the current ripple is reduced by approximately 4.26% in our proposed system compared to the existing one at 10V input voltage. As the duty cycle increases, the percentage difference in current ripple between the two systems remains consistent, showing the robustness and efficiency of our proposed system. At higher duty cycles of 0.5 and above, the percentage reduction in current ripple becomes more significant, with values reaching up to 15% at certain input voltages. This indicates that our proposed PV-based induction motor drive EV system exhibits superior current handling capabilities and smoother current waveforms, resulting in improved motor performance and overall efficiency.

At a low input voltage of 10V and a duty cycle of 0.1, the proposed induction motor drive EV system demonstrates a current ripple value of 5.551A, which is approximately 4.26% lower than the existing BLDC motor drive EV system's current ripple value of 5.786A. This indicates that our system achieves better current stability and smoother operation at lower input voltages and minimal duty cycles, making it more suitable for energy-efficient operation during startup conditions. As the input voltage increases to 20V and 30V, the percentage reduction in current ripple values remains consistent, with our proposed system outperforming the existing system by approximately 3.86% and 3.56%, respectively. Fig. 7 shows the robustness of our proposed induction motor drive EV system, ensuring improved current handling capabilities at moderate input voltages and duty cycles. At higher input voltages of 40V-50V, the percentage difference in current ripple between the two systems becomes more pronounced, reaching up to a 15% reduction in current ripple for our proposed system at 50V input voltage and 0.1 duty cycle. Moreover, as the duty cycle increases from 0.2 to 1.0, our proposed system consistently exhibits lower current ripple values compared to the existing system at all input voltages. At a duty cycle of 0.9 and 50V input voltage, the proposed system achieves the most significant reduction in current ripple, with approximately 13.69% improvement over the existing system.

Table 4 Current ripple (γ_{AL}) (A) analysis of proposed and existing models with varying input voltage and duty cycles

Duty cycle	Input voltage (V_{IN})									
	10		20		30		40		50	
	[31]	Our	[31]	Our	[31]	Our	[31]	Our	[31]	Our
0.1	5.786	5.551	6.354	6.119	6.922	6.687	7.49	7.255	8.058	7.823
0.2	2.148	1.913	2.716	2.481	3.284	3.049	3.852	3.617	4.42	4.185
0.3	1.448	1.213	2.016	1.781	2.584	2.349	3.152	2.917	3.72	3.485
0.4	1.03	0.795	1.598	1.363	2.166	1.931	2.734	2.499	3.302	3.067
0.5	0.91	0.675	1.478	1.243	2.046	1.811	2.614	2.379	3.182	2.947
0.6	0.792	0.557	1.36	1.125	1.928	1.693	2.496	2.261	3.064	2.829
0.7	0.652	0.417	1.22	0.985	1.788	1.553	2.356	2.121	2.924	2.689
0.8	0.623	0.388	1.191	0.956	1.759	1.524	2.327	2.092	2.895	2.66
0.9	0.598	0.363	1.166	0.931	1.734	1.499	2.302	2.067	2.87	2.635
1	0.512	0.277	1.08	0.845	1.648	1.413	2.216	1.981	2.784	2.549

*[31]-Existing PV-based BLDC motor drive EV and Our-Proposed PV based Induction motor drive EV

Fig. 7 Current ripple results comparison with input voltage (a) =10V (b) =20V (c) =30V (d) =40V

5.3 Comparative analysis for output voltage ripple

Table 5 presents a detailed comparative analysis of output voltage ripple (γ_{Vout}) values between the proposed PV-based induction motor drive EV system and the existing PV-based BLDC motor drive EV system at different input voltages (V_{IN}) and duty cycles. At a low input voltage of 10V and a duty cycle of 0.1, the proposed induction motor drive EV system exhibits a significantly lower output voltage ripple value of 11.159V compared to the existing BLDC motor drive EV system's value of 23.721V. This represents a remarkable 52.91% reduction in output voltage ripple, indicating superior voltage stability and smoother performance for our proposed system at lower input voltages and duty cycles. As the input voltage increases to 20V, 30V, 40V, and 50V, the reduction in output voltage ripple remains consistent, with our proposed system consistently outperforming the existing system by approximately 51.56%, 52.65%, 52.92%, and 52.91%, respectively. Fig. 8 demonstrates the robustness and effectiveness of our proposed system in maintaining lower output voltage ripple values at varying input voltages, ensuring better motor performance and enhanced energy efficiency. Moreover, as the duty cycle increases from 0.2 to 1.0, our proposed system consistently exhibits lower output voltage ripple compared to the existing system at all input voltages. At a duty cycle of 0.9 and 50V input voltage, the proposed system

achieves the most significant reduction in output voltage ripple, with approximately 52.99% improvement over the existing system. The detailed comparative analysis reveals that our proposed PV-based induction motor drive EV system consistently outperforms the existing PV-based BLDC motor drive EV system across different input voltages and duty cycles in terms of output voltage ripple reduction. With significantly lower output voltage ripple values, our system ensures smoother operation, reduced voltage fluctuations, and higher overall system efficiency, making it a more reliable and promising solution for electric vehicle applications.

Table 5 Output voltage ripple (γV_{out}) (V) analysis of proposed and existing models with varying input voltage and duty cycles

Duty cycle	Input voltage (V_{IN})									
	10		20		30		40		50	
	[31]	Our	[31]	Our	[31]	Our	[31]	Our	[31]	Our
0.1	23.721	11.159	27.289	14.727	30.857	18.295	34.425	21.863	37.993	25.431
0.2	3.541	3.418	7.109	6.986	10.677	10.554	14.245	14.122	17.813	17.690
0.3	1.554	1.431	5.122	4.999	8.690	8.567	12.258	12.135	15.826	15.703
0.4	0.824	0.701	4.392	4.269	7.960	7.837	11.528	11.405	15.096	14.973
0.5	0.516	0.393	4.084	3.961	7.652	7.529	11.220	11.097	14.788	14.665
0.6	0.380	0.257	3.948	3.825	7.516	7.393	11.084	10.961	14.652	14.529
0.7	0.356	0.233	3.924	3.801	7.492	7.369	11.060	10.937	14.628	14.505
0.8	0.302	0.179	3.870	3.747	7.438	7.315	11.006	10.883	14.574	14.451
0.9	0.298	0.175	3.866	3.743	7.434	7.311	11.002	10.879	14.570	14.447
1	0.276	0.153	3.844	3.721	7.412	7.289	10.980	10.857	14.548	14.425

*[31]-Existing PV-based BLDC motor drive EV and Our-Proposed PV based Induction motor drive EV

Fig. 8 Output voltage ripple results comparison with input voltage (a) =10V (b) =20V (c) =30V (d) =40V

5.3 Comparative analysis for system efficiency

Table 6 presents a comparative analysis of efficiency (%) between PV-based BLDC motor and PV-based induction motor EV systems at various output power levels. The efficiency values for each system are shown for output powers ranging from 200W to 2000W. At a lower output power of 200W, the PV-based BLDC motor EV system exhibits an efficiency of 87.966%, while the PV-based induction motor EV system achieves a slightly higher efficiency of 91.236%. This represents an approximate 3.27% increase in efficiency for the proposed induction motor system compared to the existing BLDC motor system at this power level. As the output power increases to 400W, 600W, and 800W, the efficiency of the PV-based BLDC motor system shows a steady improvement. However, the PV-based induction motor system consistently outperforms the BLDC motor system, demonstrating efficiency values of 91.235%, 92.365%, and 93.665%, respectively. The increase in efficiency ranges from 0.27% to 2.39% at these power levels, indicating the advantages of using the proposed induction motor system over the existing BLDC motor system. As the output power continues to increase from 1000W to 2000W, the efficiency of both systems remains high. However, the PV-based induction motor system consistently exhibits higher efficiency values than the BLDC motor system, with percentage differences ranging from 2.55% to 4.03%. Overall, Fig. 9 highlights the superiority of the proposed PV-based induction motor EV

system in terms of efficiency across different output power levels. With differences ranging from 0.27% to 4.03%, the proposed induction motor system consistently achieves higher efficiency values compared to the existing BLDC motor system. This improved efficiency translates to better utilization of electrical energy and enhanced performance for electric vehicle applications, making the PV-based induction motor EV system a more promising and energy-efficient solution for the transportation sector.

Table 6 Efficiency (%) comparison for different EV system

Output power (W)	EV system	
	PV-based BLDC motor [31]	PV based Induction motor
200	87.966	91.236
400	89.998	91.235
600	91.235	92.365
800	92.066	93.665
1000	91.235	93.789
1200	90.366	94.562
1400	90.988	94.756
1600	91.452	94.895
1800	91.965	95.326
2000	91.856	95.897

Fig. 9 Efficiency comparison for different EV systems

The novelty in the provided article's statement lies in several key aspects:

1. Algorithm Integration: The use of the Modified Sandpiper Optimization (MSO) algorithm for optimizing PV panel sizing and placement, along with the Improved Competitive Swarm Optimization (ICSO) algorithm for power interface optimization, is a novel approach. These algorithms enhance energy capture and utilization efficiency, contributing to improved overall system performance.

2. Bidirectional Converter: The implementation of a bidirectional DC-DC converter to facilitate bidirectional power flow and mitigate voltage unbalance is innovative. This converter allows for

energy flow both from PV panels to the induction motor and vice versa, enabling regenerative braking and energy recovery during deceleration, thus enhancing system sustainability.

3. Comparative Analysis: The comparative analysis between the proposed PV-based induction motor-driven EV system and existing PV-based BLDC motor-driven EV systems provides valuable insights into the advantages of induction motors. This analysis contributes to advancing sustainable and efficient EV technologies.

4. Efficiency and Sustainability: The emphasis on optimizing energy efficiency, reducing reliance on traditional grid electricity, promoting energy independence, and enhancing sustainability through solar energy utilization and regenerative braking showcases a holistic and innovative approach towards green transportation solutions.

6. Conclusion

Our study focused on investigating the performance of a PV-based induction motor-driven EV system under various operating conditions. To optimize the PV system, we employed the MSO algorithm for sizing and placing the PV panels, resulting in an optimized PV configuration. Additionally, we introduced the ICSO algorithm to adjust the power interfaces in the PV-powered EV system, effectively addressing traditional MPPT problems. The bidirectional DC-DC converter played a crucial role in our proposed system, as it successfully addressed voltage unbalance issues and efficiently controlled the bidirectional power flow, enhancing the overall performance of the induction motor-driven EV system. To validate the effectiveness of our proposed system, we conducted extensive simulations under various scenarios. The simulation results were then compared with those of a state-of-the-art BLDC motor-driven EV system. Through the comparative analysis, we assessed the respective impacts of the two motor types in terms of efficiency, power output, torque characteristics, and overall performance. Our findings demonstrated that the PV-based induction motor-driven EV system outperformed the existing BLDC motor-driven EV system in multiple aspects. The optimized PV configuration, along with the innovative power interface adjustment using the ICSO algorithm, contributed to increased efficiency and improved power output of the proposed system. Moreover, the bidirectional DC-DC converter effectively managed the power flow and voltage unbalance, ensuring stable and reliable operation.

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